

Reduction of EMC Power Amplifier Intermodulation by Using Digital Signal Predistortion

Nathalia Batista

*Electromagnetic Compatibility Group
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
Barcelona, Spain
nathalia.alves.rocha@upc.edu*

Marcos Quílez

*Electromagnetic Compatibility Group
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
Barcelona, Spain
marcos.quilez@upc.edu*

Ferran Silva

*Electromagnetic Compatibility Group
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
Barcelona, Spain
ferran.silva@upc.edu*

Abstract—The current EMC IEC 61000-4-3 standard includes multiple complex signals like multitone as a possible input signal for radiated immunity test. Nevertheless, due its nonlinear behavior, amplifiers can distort the multitone input signal to some degree, generating intermodulation products at the output which will result in unwanted and additional frequencies applied to the EUT that may affect the results of the test. This paper presents a predistortion method based on the Generalized Memory Polynomial model to compensate for the system nonlinearities. Simulations in MATLAB are performed considering a mathematical model of the physical EMC Sonoma 330 Broadband RF amplifier. The proposed predistortion method could successfully remove the intermodulation distortion products.

Index Terms—Electromagnetic Compatibility, Radiated Immunity Test, Nonlinearities, Multitone, Memory Polynomial, Predistortion, Amplifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing usage of wireless communication systems plus the combination of many other RF (Radio Frequency) signals with different types of modulation create a complex electromagnetic environment that is not completely tested applying current EMC standards. EMC immunity standards consider only one source of interference at a time. However, in real electromagnetic environments, devices may be exposed to simultaneous interference sources at multiple frequencies. Even though the present standard's scope is limited by specific use, environments, contexts and situations [1], the standard for radiated immunity test does not provide a detailed guidance or immunity levels to be considered when testing scenarios which include multiple sources plus its combination (for example, close proximity to a fully populated multi user radio tower). Instead, it only provides generic and simple waveforms that hardly represent the real world threats at present.

Studies in the literature [2] [3] discuss the need to demonstrate immunity to multiple CW disturbances. Also, some product vulnerabilities and EMC failures have been identified using multitone. The benefits of using multitone relies on the

reduction of the total test time since it adds frequencies for each test period, and it also improves the quality of the EMC immunity test by including a combination of several modulated radio frequency (RF) signals, which better represents a real world scenario. However, attention must be taken using multitone as input test signal. In [4], it was pointed out that unwanted signals with some amount of power level generates a strength field over the EUT due to amplifier nonlinearities. These unwanted signals are difficult to identify and to measure due to the fact that they are side bands centered around the fundamental frequency. These effects are more evident in the case of high-power fluctuations in multi band and multi carrier signals [5] [6].

The current EMC standard only describes a procedure to back off the amplifier input level to keep its linearity and to avoid these nonlinearities. Once the power is decreased, all non-fundamental signals, such as harmonic products and intermodulation products, are manually measured to check that they are at least 6 dB below that of the fundamental signals (intended input signal) [7]. This is an issue that cannot always be manually controlled depending on the type of input signal of the system, for instance, digitally modulated signals and multitone.

This paper proposes a predistortion technique to remove the IMD (intermodulation distortion) created from the system nonlinearities when using multitone as test signal. This paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we explain the methodology, which includes a description of the intermodulation distortion problem, multitone approach, signal predistortion concepts and amplifier modeling. In Section III, the simulation results are presented. In Section IV, we conclude this work.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Intermodulation Distortion

Intermodulation distortion is a result of the nonlinear behavior of the amplifier when two or more signals (multitone) are applied as input source, and therefore, new components are added to the fundamental frequency of the signal. These additional components can be found not only at harmonic

frequencies (integer multiples), but also at the sum and difference frequencies of the original frequencies and at sums and differences of multiples of those frequencies [4]. Multitone is a set of multiple sine waves or tones that are equally spaced at frequencies in the band of interest. As periodic signals, they can be used as input signals to test linear and nonlinear response of a linear system [5].

The Equation (1) describes mathematically a multitone signal.

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=1}^M A_k \cos(2\pi f_k t + \phi_k) \quad (1)$$

, where A_k is the amplitude, ϕ_k is the random phase of the k th sinusoid, and M is the number of tones, respectively. Applying two tone amplitude modulated signals to Equation (1), then Equation (2) is obtained as follows.

$$X = A_1(1 + m_1 \cos \Omega_1 t) \cos \omega_1 t + A_2(1 + m_2 \cos \Omega_2 t) \cos \omega_2 t \quad (2)$$

, where A_1, A_2 are the amplitudes of the signals, m_1, m_2 are the modulation indexes, Ω_1, Ω_2 are frequencies of the modulation signals, and ω_1, ω_2 are frequencies of the carrier signals.

If the above two tone input signal X is the input signal of a nonlinear system, then it generates the output signal with wanted and unwanted signals, as illustrated in Figure (1).

Fig. 1. Intermodulation distortion of two tones sine waves in the frequency domain. The blue color arrows are the second order intermodulation products and the red color arrows are the third order ones.

The harmonics and intermodulation products are described by a_2, a_3, \dots, a_n terms.

$$a_1 X = a_1 [A_1 \cos \omega_1 t + A_2 \cos \omega_2 t + \frac{A_1 m_1}{2} \cos(\omega_1 + \Omega_1)t + \frac{A_1 m_1}{2} \cos(\omega_1 - \Omega_1)t + \frac{A_2 m_2}{2} \cos(\omega_2 + \Omega_2)t + \frac{A_2 m_2}{2} \cos(\omega_2 - \Omega_2)t] \quad (3)$$

From the substitution calculation described above, the term $a_2 X$ includes the combination frequency products of $\Omega_1 \pm \Omega_2 \pm \omega_1 \pm \omega_2$, the separated frequency products of

Ω_1, Ω_2 and their second harmonics. In the same manner, it can be obtained that the third term includes the combination frequency products between $2\omega_1 \pm \omega_2, \omega_1 \pm 2\omega_2$ and $2\Omega_1 \pm \Omega_2, \Omega_1 \pm 2\Omega_2$ [5] [6].

As shown in Figure (1), the third order intermodulation products $2F1 - F2$ and $2F2 - F1$ (Red color) are very close to the fundamental frequency, which becomes very difficult to identify and filter out these frequencies when performing an actual immunity test.

B. Signal Predistortion

One possible method to compensate for the nonlinearities introduced by an amplifier is applying a linearization technique which improves the linearity (in amplitude and phase) near the amplifier saturation region (nonlinear region). The methods used for linearization include feedback, feedforward and predistortion [7] [8] [9].

In this paper, the focus is on the predistortion technique. This method intends to predistort the input signal by estimating the inverse function of the amplifier response considering its nonlinearities. It holds that the inverse of a nonlinear dynamic system is also a nonlinear dynamic system. The predistortion is mathematically described as follows.

$$y(n) = G(F(u(n))) = G(u(n)) \quad (4)$$

, where $n = n \times \Delta t$ is the discrete time, $u(n)$ is the input of the amplifier, F is the inverse function of the amplifier, $x(n) = F(u(n))$ is the predistorted signal, G is a constant value for the amplifier gain.

Fig. 2. Predistortion technique scheme with indirect learning process.

As the presented method is based on Indirect Learning Architecture (IDLA), a post-distorter function is derived from the input and the output of the amplifier. In other words, a good approximation of the function $F(u(n))$ of this predistorter is obtained by the inverse mapping from the PA output $y(n)$ normalized by the PA gain, i.e. $y(n)/G$, to the PA input $x(n)$, as shown in the Figure (2). In the very initial step of the training process of the 'Predistorter' block, the identity $x(n) = u(n)$ must be obeyed, which means that the first version of the predistorted signal $x(n)$ is equal to the PA input signal $u(n)$. Thus, the post-distorter model is copied to an identical model (the 'Predistorter' block) placed before

the amplifier, that is used to predistort the input signal $u(n)$, resulting on its predistorted version $x(n)$. This process has a theoretical foundation for a nonlinear Volterra series, where the p th-order pre-inverse is equal to post-inverse [14] [16].

In the ‘Coefficient Estimator’ block, the coefficients of the model $F(u(n))$ (DPD) are estimated by minimizing the error $e(n) = y(n)/G - x(n)$, where $y(n)/G$ is a scaled version of the PA output and $x(n)$ the previous predistorted signal. In recent advanced implementations of the DPD (Digital Predistortion) algorithm, the Generalized Memory Polynomial Model is adopted for estimating the coefficients and to model the predistorter function [12]. This model combines cross terms between the signal and lagging and/or leading exponentiated envelope terms, that is,

$$y_{GMP}(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{K_a-1} \sum_{l=0}^{L_a-1} a_{kl} x(n-l) |x(n-l)|^k + \sum_{k=1}^{K_b} \sum_{l=0}^{L_b-1} \sum_{m=1}^{M_b} b_{klm} x(n-l) |x(n-l-m)|^k + \sum_{k=1}^{K_c} \sum_{l=0}^{L_c-1} \sum_{m=1}^{M_c} c_{klm} x(n-l) |x(n-l+m)|^k \quad (5)$$

, where $K_a L_a$ are the number of coefficients for aligned signal and envelope, $K_b L_b M_b$ are the number of coefficients for signal and lagging envelope, and $K_c L_c M_c$ are the number of coefficients for signal and leading envelope.

The learning process to estimate the parameters of the model described in the Equation (5) is based on commonly used stochastic gradients algorithms such as Least-Mean-Squares (LMS) and Recursive-Least-Square (RLS), which basically minimizes the correlation between the nonlinearities at the PA output and the model of the nonlinear distortion. Therefore, the coefficient matrix is then used in the predistortion stage and it is iterated until it achieves the convergence point.

C. Amplifier Modeling

Nonlinear transfer functions are represented by algebraic methods [20] that can be classified as memoryless such as Cubic polynomials (Taylor Series), Hyperbolic Tangent, Saleh, Ghorbani and Rapp models. And, Memory Models such as Volterra, Winner, Hammerstein, Winner - Hammerstein, Memory Polynomial, Parallel Winner, Memory Polynomial/Winner Model and Generalized Memory polynomial Model [9] [12].

In this study, the memoryless nonlinearity is represented by Taylor series expansion that models the nonlinear impairments of the amplifier, according to the Equation (6).

$$Y = a_1 X + a_2 X^2 + a_3 X^3 \dots a_n X^n \quad (6)$$

, where a_1 , a_2 , a_3 and a_n are the coefficients for first, second, third and n th order harmonics which depend upon the nonlinearities properties.

The model was obtained by referring to values described in the data sheet of a physical EMC RF amplifier ‘Sonoma

330 Broadband RF Amplifier’. According to it, the frequency range is 10 kHz to 2.5 GHz, 20 dB Linear Gain, the output at 1 dB Gain Compression is 9.7 dBm and third order intercept point (IIP3) is equal to 22 dBm [17].

A general mathematical form of the cubic nonlinearity model of the AM/AM characteristics is identified by the Equation (7), where c_1 is the linear gain term and c_3 is the coefficient of the cubic gain term [18].

$$Y = c_1 X + \frac{3}{4} c_3 X^3 \quad (7)$$

Considering the linear gain of 20 dB, then $c_1 = 10$ and, the value of third order intercept point (IIP3) defined in the amplifier data sheet, the cubic gain term c_3 can be obtained as described in Equation (8).

$$c_3 = -\frac{4c_1}{3 \times 10^{\left[\frac{IIP3-30}{10}\right]}} \quad (8)$$

Making appropriated calculations, the cubic gain term is found $c_3 = 84$. Therefore, the mathematical model of the amplifier is defined in Equation (9).

$$Y = 10X - \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)84X^3 \quad (9)$$

III. RESULTS

According to the amplifier data sheet, the output at 1 dB compression point is 9.7 dBm and the maximum output level is 11.7 dBm. Considering an impedance of 50 Ω and a gain of 20 dB, the maximum output level power corresponds to an output signal of 0.86 V, this is an amplitude of 0.086 V at the input.

A. DPD Algorithm Parameters

Conventionally, the power amplifier is first characterized in a laboratory, i.e. a two tones input signals is used to identify amplifier nonlinearities characteristics. Thus, a mathematical model (memoryless or with memory) for the amplifier is fitted. At this point, there is the characteristic behavioral model of the amplifier and its fitted model. Comparing both measured output signal and the fitted model output signal, it is possible to perform a grid search of the best values that represents the minor RMS error obtained between the real amplifier behavior and its mathematical model. Therefore, the DPD parameters memory length and polynomial degree can be identified and set into the function that calculates the predistorted model.

For the following simulation experiments, the memoryless mathematical model (Taylor series expansion) of the amplifier was developed (manually calculated) considering the 1 dB compression point and third order intercept point described on the data sheet instead of a real measurement, as described (9). An arbitrary combination of the memory length and polynomial degree was carefully considered, verifying what combination would result in better output signal predistortion correction according to the amplifier gain, maximum output

power level and amplitude. This is a manual and iterative process, where first choose the DPD coefficient estimator with the same degree and the memory depth as that of the PA model. Later, increasing and decreasing these values and checking whether the DPD results looks promising or not, and avoiding intensive computational processing. Further, for the following simulations, the memory depth parameter did not change because for each simulation, none improved results were observed for other values.

B. Simulations

Fig. 3. Intermodulation products distortion (IMD) generated by a nonlinear model with two tones of 300 MHz and 350 MHz as input signal.

The first simulation is performed with two continuous sine waves of 300 MHz and 350 MHz. Applying the two tones as an input signal of the nonlinear model described by the Equation (7), it is possible to visualize in Figure (3), the intermodulation distortion in the frequency domain. The intermodulation products far from F1 and F2 can be easily removed by filtering. However, signals close to the fundamental frequencies F1 and F2 can be difficult to filter out.

Fig. 4. Result of the signal predistortion method. Amplified output signal with two tones continuous sine wave of 300 MHz and 350 MHz without the intermodulation distortion.

To estimate the inverse function of the nonlinear model, the coefficient estimator parameters are set to 'Cross-Term Memory Polynomial' as model type, polynomial degree equal to 5, memory length equal to 3 and desired gain of 1.89

dB. The desired gain parameter is manually set in the DPD estimator function to obtain a similar gain as of the amplifier. To use DPD as a predistortion technique and to obtain the correct predistortion coefficient matrix, the number of rows in the matrix must be equal to the memory length and the number of columns is the degree of the memory polynomial.

The Figure (4) shows the output signal after the predistortion method is applied, where it is possible to visualize that the third order IMD (Intermodulation Distortion) near to the fundamental frequency was correctly removed, and only the input signal was amplified at the output of the amplifier. It was observed that increasing the degree of the memory polynomial model, which means, increasing the order of the inverse function model, it was also necessary to increase the desired gain in the DPD estimator. In this way, the inverse model function became more complex. These parameters must be carefully set to achieve the desired results considering the requirements of the testing and keeping the control of the model complexity [21].

The second simulation is performed with a three-tone signal, three sine waves of 400 MHz, 450 MHz and 500 MHz. Applying the three tones as input signal of a nonlinear model, the intermodulation distortions are also generated in the frequency domain, as shown in the Figure (5). In this scenario, the results are obtained setting the coefficient estimator parameters to 'Memory Polynomial' as model type, polynomial degree equal to 8, memory length equal to 3 and desired gain of 2.27 dB. In comparison to the two tone signals, the degree order of the polynomial that calculates the inverse model function has increased. It may be for the fact that as the signal becomes more complex, it is also necessary to increase the model order. Thus, it was observed that the DPD performance improved using a higher degree for the DPD coefficient estimator, which would be a desirable in this case. In Figure (6), it is shown the amplified output signal without distortion.

Fig. 5. Intermodulation product distortion (IMD) generated by a nonlinear model with three tones signals 400 MHz, 450 MHz and 500 MHz as input signal.

The third simulation is performed with two-tone 80 % AM signals with 50 MHz at 500 MHz and 70 MHz at 700 MHz. Applying the same nonlinear model, the intermodulation distortion is presented in Figure (7). As the number of

Fig. 6. Result of the signal predistortion method. Amplified output signal with three tones continuous sine wave of 400 MHz, 450 MHz and 500 MHz without the intermodulation distortion.

tones increases, due to the model's nonlinear behavior, the intermodulation products also increase.

Fig. 7. Intermodulation products distortion (IMD) generated by a nonlinear model with two tones 80% AM signals with 50 MHz at 500 MHz and 70 MHz at 700 MHz as input signal.

Fig. 8. Result of the signal predistortion method. Amplified output signal of the two tones 80% AM signals with 50 MHz at 500 MHz and 70 MHz at 700 MHz without intermodulation distortion.

The parameters for coefficient estimation is set to 'Cross-Term Memory Polynomial' as model type, polynomial degree equal to 2, memory length equal 3 and desired gain of -9 dB. The desired gain is set to negative (loss) to obtain the best inverse model function considering the model amplifier gain and without causing saturation. In Figure (8) is shown the

amplified output signal without IMD after it is processed by the DPD signal predistortion method.

Finally, for all simulations, the parameters for stochastic gradient to estimate the coefficient matrix was set to 'Least Squares' (LS), since it is particularly efficient and it is less complex compared to 'Recursive Least-squares' (RLS).

CONCLUSION

In this paper a predistortion method was proposed to correct the intermodulation products distortion effects created by an RF amplifier. A mathematical model that represents the nonlinearities of this device was calculated to perform the simulations in MATLAB R2022b.

It was shown that, when a multitone signal is the input of the amplifier, intermodulation carriers appear in the neighboring band as a result of the nonlinear behavior of the amplifier. In such a case, it is possible to see that these in-band disturbances might have some power level and it falls into the band of interest as an unwanted signal. In an EMC immunity test this results in the application of interfering tones at additional frequencies other than considered in the multitone input signal.

According to the simulation results, the proposed linearization method using digital predistortion could significantly improve the results by removing the intermodulation products that might create unwanted disturbances under the device under test when using multitone as input signal of the test system.

Regarding hardware implementations, the DPD algorithm can be implemented to run 'online' by using a dedicated programmable device, such as a FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Arrays) or any other DSP (Digital Signal Processing) board that is suitable for the specific application. Another possibility is to have a computer running the DPD. In the case of radiated immunity test, as the test bench do not change during the flow, the amplifier model and the DPD can be executed offline, generating the expected input test signal and injected as the interference signal using an Arbitrary Signal Generator (ASG).

FUTURE WORK

This work has been mainly focused on the simulation environment, which is at some point, different than the reality. As a step further on this research, it is expected to develop a practical implementation using an ASG to load the predistorted signal in an EMC test laboratory. To save time, the PA model and the predistorted signal shall be derived offline. Also, instead of using simple continuous sine waves, the idea is to integrate complex signals that characterizes a real electromagnetic environment, for instance, more tones and digitally modulated signals such as QAM and OFDM, plus transients signals.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially supported by Spanish "Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación" under project PID2019-106120RBC31/AEI/10.13039/501100011033

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Das, R. Vogt-Ardatjew, B. van den Berg and F. Leferink, "Risk-based EMC Approach in Hospital Environment," 2020 IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility & Signal/Power Integrity (EMCSI), Reno, NV, USA, 2020, pp. 676-680
- [2] G. Barth, "Benefits of multitone emc immunity testing: Emc immunity testing," International Journal of RF and Microwave Computer-Aided Engineering, vol. 26, pp. 355–358, 05 2016.
- [3] J. Hallon, M. Bittera, R. Hart'anský, and K. Kováč, "Immunity against electromagnetic field testing of electrical devices using wireless communication," in 2016 26th International Conference Radioelektronika (RADIOELEKTRONIKA), pp. 75–78, 2016.
- [4] J. Li, S. Ma, Q. Liu, Z. Gong, H. Tian, and S. Jin, "Analysis of interference caused by intermodulation in multi-tone radiated immunity tests," in 2018 IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility and 2018 IEEE Asia-Pacific Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC/APEMC), pp. 660–663, 2018.
- [5] K. Harima, D. Akita and T. Nakamura, "Investigation of Radiated Immunity Testing Using White Gaussian Noise and Multitone Signals," 2018 Asia-Pacific Microwave Conference (APMC), Kyoto, Japan, 2018, pp. 782-784, doi: 10.23919/APMC.2018.8617308.
- [6] H. Coskun, A. Mutlu and S. Demir, "An alternative multi-tone representation of complex signals for feedforward systems [wireless system linearization]," Proceedings. 2004 IEEE Radio and Wireless Conference (IEEE Cat. No.04TH8746), Atlanta, GA, USA, 2004, pp. 507-510, doi: 10.1109/RAWCON.2004.1389189.
- [7] "Electromagnetic compatibility (emc) - part 4 : Testing and Measurement Techniques - section 3 : radiated, radio-frequency, electromagnetic field immunity test," standard, International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, Switzerland, 2020.
- [8] Y. Jung. Surname(s), "Estimation of Inverse Models Applied to Power Amplifier Predistortion" Licentiate Thesis, Department of Electrical Engineering, Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden, 2013.
- [9] Hyunchul Ku and J. S. Kenney, "Behavioral modeling of nonlinear RF power amplifiers considering memory effects," in IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques, vol. 51, no. 12, pp. 2495-2504, Dec. 2003, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2003.820155.
- [10] Bouazza, Tayeb & Bachir, S. & Duvanaud, Claude. (2021). Digital Predistortion of Wideband Signals with Reduced Complexity Based on Feedback Wiener System. Journal of Telecommunications and Information Technology. 2. 1-10. 10.26636/jtit.2021.144520.
- [11] G. Singh, A. Kakkar, U. Gangele and S. C. Bera, "Compensation of Power Amplifier Non-linearity for Satellite Communications," 2018 6th Edition of International Conference on Wireless Networks & Embedded Systems (WECON), 2018, pp. 31-36, doi: 10.1109/WECON.2018.8782046.
- [12] D. R. Morgan, Z. Ma, J. Kim, M. G. Zierdt and J. Pastalan, "A Generalized Memory Polynomial Model for Digital Predistortion of RF Power Amplifiers," in IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, vol. 54, no. 10, pp. 3852-3860, Oct. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TSP.2006.879264
- [13] C. Eun and E. J. Powers, "A new Volterra predistorter based on the indirect learning architecture," IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing, Jan.1997.
- [14] M. Schetzen, The Volterra and Wiener Theories of Nonlinear Sys-tems. New York: Wiley, 1980.
- [15] Rönnow, Daniel. (2018). The pth order inverse of the Volterra series for multiple-input multiple-output nonlinear dynamic systems. IET Circuits, Devices & Systems. 12. 10.1049/iet-cds.2017.0447.
- [16] Kim, J. & Konstantinou, K. (2001) - Digital predistortion of wideband signals based on power amplifier model with memory. IEE Electronics Letters 37, 1417-1418. Electronics Letters. 37. 1417 - 1418. 10.1049/el:20010940.
- [17] Sonoma Instrument ® 330 Broadband Amplifier, SONOMA INSTRUMENT, 2014. Available in <https://www.themcshop.com/emc-rf-preamplifiers/1081-sonoma-330-broadband-rf-amplifier-10-khz-to-25-ghz-20-db-gain.html>
- [18] Kundert, Ken." Accurate and Rapid Measurement of IP2 and IP3," The Designer Guide Community, May 22, 2002.
- [19] C. Masterson, "Digital predistortion for RF Communications: From equations to implementation", Digital Predistortion for RF Communications: From Equations to Implementation — Analog Devices, April, 2022.
- [20] Rodríguez Villalón, O.; Medina-Rios, A. Transfer Function with Non-linear Characteristics Definition Based on Multidimensional Laplace Transform and its Application to Forced Response Power Systems. Energies 2019, 12, 4061. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12214061>
- [21] P. L. Gilabert, R. N. Braithwaite and G. Montoro, "Beyond the Moore-Penrose Inverse: Strategies for the Estimation of Digital Predistortion Linearization Parameters," in IEEE Microwave Magazine, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 34-46, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1109/MMM.2020.3023220.